

PRACTICAL DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS OF ORGANIZATION OF TALENTED STUDENTS' CONTEST

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Abstract. Due to the wide range of high opportunities in students, their uniqueness, the availability of a wide range of mental and physical opportunities, various social problems eliminate the factors that can negatively affect their development due to increased attention to them in society. Therefore, there is a need to properly select gifted students to prevent them from being overlooked or to be protected from certain social problems. Probably, these ideas are at the heart of the selection of talented young people in our society and around the world and providing them with content-rich education. Therefore, the effective organization of the education of students selected on the basis of scientifically based and content-based methodologies is a topical issue and on this basis requires a number of practical work. This article shows the scientific and pedagogical issues, the psychological basis for the selection of gifted students in the field of science among senior students of specialized schools, and the study introduced special methods for the selection of gifted students in literature in specialized schools. The number of subjects is 265. This article is intended for professionals, undergraduate and graduate students majoring in pedagogy and psychology, senior researchers, and researchers conducting research.

Keywords: psychology, talent, aptitude, accelerated education, methodology, specialized schools, qualifying, dictation.

ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ РАЗРАБОТКА МЕТОДИКИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ КОНКУРСА ТАЛАНТЛИВЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. Благодаря широкому спектру высоких возможностей у студентов, их уникальности, наличию широкого круга умственных и физических возможностей, различные социальные проблемы устраняют факторы, способные негативно повлиять на их развитие, за счет повышенного внимания к ним в обществе. Поэтому возникает необходимость в правильном отборе одаренных учащихся, чтобы не допустить их игнорирования или оградить от тех или иных социальных проблем. Вероятно, эти идеи лежат в основе отбора талантливой молодежи в нашем обществе и во всем мире и предоставления им содержательного образования. Поэтому эффективная организация обучения студентов, отобранных на основе научно-обоснованных и содержательных методик, является актуальным вопросом и на этой основе требует проведения ряда практических работ. В данной статье показаны научно-педагогические вопросы, психологические основы отбор одаренных в области наук среди учащихся старших классов специальных школ, а также введение в исследование специальных методов отбора одаренных учащихся по литературе в специализированных школах. Количество тем – 265. Статья предназначена для специалистов, студентов и аспирантов педагогических и психологических специальностей, старших научных сотрудников и научных сотрудников, проводящих исследования.

Ключевые слова: психология, талант, способности, ускоренное обучение, методика, специализированные школы, квалификация, диктант.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that school education consists of many requirements and obligations that arise from the abilities of students. Everyone at school age begins to receive from this place a vital and elementary scientific education in accordance with their capabilities. But in school conditions, each child does not have the opportunity to have a separate education and a separate upbringing, corresponding to his abilities and abilities. At the same time, each child is considered one of the important and urgent tasks of the school community to develop, uncover in himself a world, its potential, hidden opportunities.

In this regard, the idea of stratification training is included. But the teaching of strata has its own problems and a number of deviations have been observed in this area. Nevertheless, some areas of stratification training can be used for positive purposes (Shumakova N. The B. of "Constellation" ("Sozvezdie") school laboratory) [14]. Indeed, depending on the professional orientation of the children, there are schools in which specialized areas of education, such as the direction of Natural Sciences, the direction of humanities, or the education of children with a tendency to languages, are in a form that does not undermine human dignity, and exactly contribute significantly to the rapid development of our children. For this purpose, the establishment of specialized schools in our Republic is defined by the law "on education". Today, special schools that are compatible with the interests, aspirations and aspirations of our children operate in every province, district. The functioning of these schools is undoubtedly a positive reality, it will rid children of the same teaching who have the opportunity to take different directions and education, provide diversity in education.

But the answer to the question of WHO and how should be taught in these specialized schools determines the social, spiritual, economic essence of these schools. The effectiveness of these schools can be reduced to zero if the children from among the specialized schools have a tendency, ability, interest and enthusiasm for the relevant specialty, and the children with a positive ability are not selected. Either the scientifically based methodological system of teaching children in the classrooms, the teacher who has passed special training, or if there is no perfect system of education, the existence of this school may not justify itself.

It should be noted in this place that such words asidoridor, ability and talent are close to each other, but differ in their meaning, are used in the people's mouth in many, sometimes without any difference. Words of talent and talent are the main categories of psychology, which are among the scientific expressions. In its own sense, these words provide for a wide and successful application of human capabilities in the social environment. A talented person is extremely successful, progressive, intelligent in a certain field, and in his nature a complex of unique opportunities operates. Idoridor SOR is a phrase used in the Uzbek language from ancient times and is spoken in relation to people who have property, husband and potential [5].

At the moment, the wordidoridor is spoken in relation to advanced, moving, knowledgeable readers. So there is a difference in meaning between the phrases "gifted pupil" and "gifted pupil": in the so-called gifted, the pupil is taught in a certain area (for example, in mathematics, poetry, painting, etc.) the z.) it is implied that they have proven, diagnosed abilities. On this place it is called the reader who has a leader, a diligent, active, progressive reader who works a lot on his own, sometimes the public is taken into consideration by the reader. That is, idoridor soy can be applied to all advanced, active readers in a broad sense. A capable reader, in a much narrower sense, is a concrete child and meets more scientific requirements to be applied to a child who has the ability in a specific field. Talent is the manifestation of this extremely developed, versatile set of abilities [5].

Although the client, interest and upbringing of all children are manifested differently, the common feature inherent in this category of children and adolescents is the presence of a high level of mastering, learning opportunities in them.

IQT the choice and education of senior students requires us to first analyze in part their personality qualities, the specificity of their cognitive abilities and the process of life surrounded by social problems.

According to the research conducted, the main criterion for the manifestation of iqtidor children's own abilities is the uniqueness of the system of motivations in them. Activity in the priority system of such persons, including cognitive activity, occupies a special place and constitutes the content of exactly these abilities. High passion, ambition and personal approach of children with disabilities to the subject of activity are their literal interests [3,15].

In children with gonorrhea, it is possible to observe extreme excitability, which is not characteristic of its age, an emotional sensation manifested in various forms associated with it. Events that seem to be typical for ordinary children are perceived as events that are too bright for talented children, Rich in experiences, sometimes capable of changing their way of life. The manifestation of such cases is L.S.Vigotsky and A.N.Y.It is also partially connected with the censoring period, which is emphasized in the research work of leontevs. These optimal time intervals are classified by scientists in three forms of the sentimental period. These indicate the period of rapid development of speech censorship, the period of formation of Model thinking and the periods of scientific thinking censorship [4].

In many children with ADHD, it is possible to observe the state of perfectionism, that is, the desire to achieve high skills in the performance of some kind of activity. Sometimes, it is possible to observe that the iqtidor boy is repeating the work (essay, picture, model or other), which he has completed for hours, until he is satisfied with himself. Although such a virtue has a positive connotation for the further achievement of higher skills of the child, but it should be borne in mind that teachers and psychologists should monitor the presence of such children in the norm of extreme self-esteem, otherwise such a situation will lead to such negative qualities as a child's laziness, inability to complete the

IQT the self-assessment of children with disabilities, their imagination about how to properly assess their own strength and opportunities is of paramount importance. Self-assessment of children and adolescents in this category, it is natural. In children, subtle tempering properties appear. In such cases, children who are accustomed to a stable high assessment of themselves require a little "vigilance", while children who are prone to a low assessment without stability, on the contrary, feel the need for psychological support [8].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In some studies, the development of techniques for determining fertility began with the psychodiagnostics of the individual differences of children and mainly their creative abilities. Initially, only techniques that differ in creative capacity and individuality were created [1,2]. But taking into account the High opportunities in the students, it requires the formation of convincing complexes of selection methods and the introduction of Valid methods of correct selection of students of the same proportions.

In this regard, the study of the personality traits of such children, the opportunities for their own development, the formation and development of their dignity and abilities, undoubtedly, has both theoretical and practical significance.

For this purpose, we have attracted 265 students of the 7th class of the Republican specialized boarding school for music and art to our experiments. It is known that this boarding

school has an air of art and music, to some extent, children who show themselves are taken from the 5th grade. It is for this reason that the pupils of this school are considered leaders in their schools. And to a specialized school can be called, Where experienced teachers receive future students through pedagogical tests, and aspiring children who have an enthusiasm for literature, art, music are distinguished.

Thus, we aimed to sort out those children who were called iqtidorly, that is, among those who are relatively demanding, active, considerate children in the educational process, are able to meet certain requirements, are psychologically considered, have achieved high results from some aptitude tests, learn how or develop them in the educational process, and plan to study their psychological and personal characteristics in the

In order to qualify children who meet high requirements with the help of psychological tests, that is, with the help of methods of scientific psychological measurement, among specialized school students called *iqtidorli*, we used the following methods.

Method of selection of class ingenuity [6]. This methodology allows you to qualify advanced students of the class. One of the sociometric methods of diagnosing mental *zacovat* is the "method of selecting class intelligences", which is among the Valid methods in our national environment. The original idea of the methodology is to distinguish intelligentsia within the framework of the direction between the pupils of the class by asking, in an anonymous way.

It is known that students in one group know each other better than teachers, and in some cases even better than their parents. Based on this, the method of generating a generalized Image by asking themselves about the interests and aspirations of children in the class was adopted as the original idea of this methodology.

The basis of the methodology is an answer sheet consisting of seven questions, called "Do you know your class", and the examiners are required to think, think and write an unbiased answer to these questions. The examiners write the names and surnames of the most intelligent, diligent and knowledgeable children in the class from one to three, giving importance to the content of each question in the answer sheet.

The content of the process testifies that the general level of intelligence and culture of the "star", separated from each class, the position held in the class, is taken in relation to the level of the same class, at the prices of students of the same class.

The experiment will last 10-15 minutes with a break. As soon as the answer sheets are collected quickly, the class can continue to access its turn functions.

Methods "100 words" and "50 sentences" [6].

Methods "100 words" and "50 sentences" aimed at studying the level of literacy at the qualifying stage of the study were created in the Republican Talent Center in 1995. The methodology is designed to determine the level of literacy of the students.

It is known that some readers will be very sensitive to words, their exact pronunciation, correct writing. And someone else, knowing some words—unknowingly, uses them with an assumption and does not pay much attention to their correct spelling. There are also other schoolchildren who do not know or do not attach importance to the fact that there may be a difference between the pronunciation of a word and its writing, and also ignore the rules of spelling.

The "literacy" test is divided into two parts. The first part consists of 100 words, with special errors included in their 50 theses. The remaining 50 are words that meet all the requirements of the Uzbek spelling dictionary. The answer sheet of the methodology is drawn up

in the form of a table, after the ordinal number of words, two blank tiers are given. The Examiner answers by specifying an empty checkbox, after determining whether the word is correct or not.

In the first place, the examiner must carefully read the instruction for the performance of the assignment on the answer sheet and perform the task given for the sample there. On this basis is dressing ability to perform the test task on the Examiner.

It is explained to the Examiner that after reading each word and consciously determining whether it is written correctly or not, it is necessary to mark the circle under the first checkbox (t-the correct sign) and if the word is written incorrectly, then under the second checkbox (n-the wrong sign) with a coloring. As you know, it is also possible that students sometimes mistakenly mark the word that is written correctly, and the wrong word, not knowing what is wrong, is also correct. For this reason, correctly and incorrectly written words are confused in a sequence that requires them to know, to know, to think and remember, whether they are right wrong. Obviously this requires literacy from the reader. The one who knows the composition of the word, or rather its incorrect spelling, will achieve greater success.

According to the methodology, both the wrong word as an error and the wrong word as an error also affect the score of the student who scored on the same test.

With a simple counting method and counting from one point for each correct answer, after determining how many correct words are correct and how many incorrectly written words are wrong, the total result of each child is expressed in one number. This indicator is the main indicator of the methodology of 100 words.

In the second test of literacy, 50 sentences are given, these sentences are taken from the works of representatives of Uzbek literature. Sentences fully meet the rules of Uzbek spelling. But in 20 sentences, special errors were introduced, for example, a comma was removed from several sentences, in some words one letter was dropped, the word with a capital letter was written with a small letter, etc. Each sentence was divided into four parts with a vertical hyphen. And on the answer sheet, lines consisting of five circles corresponding to 50 sentences were given. After the examiner determines in which part of the sentence there is an error, paints the corresponding of the circles located on the corresponding line in the answer sheet (from 1 to 4) and determines which part the error is. If there is no error in the sentence, then the fifth circle is painted.

As we said, each sentence in the text of the questionnaire was divided into four parts with a vertical hyphen, and each part was marked with the letters A, V, S, D, respectively, on top. In other words, an error in any part of the sentence can be caused by the fact that the word or punctuation mark is incorrectly put or not put. If, in the eyes of the examiner of the sentence, for example, any word in Part V is written incorrectly, it means that it determines the V-fold of the answer sheet, and so on. If, in the eyes of the Examiner, there is also no error in the predicate part of the sentence, then it will determine the e checkbox of the corresponding line in the answer sheet. That is, there is no mistake in the sentence, it will be the one who gave the correct written answer.

This test also takes into account the amount of correct sentences that are found to be correct, as well as the fact that an error-free sentence is defined as an error-free. But unlike the first test, each correct answer is given two points. Then the results of both literacy tests will be from 100 points and it will be easier to compare and understand each other.

The dictation. Great attention is paid to the development of students' speech, including their written speech, in secondary schools. Several types of written work are used, with the

intention of cultivating the written speech of the readers, making them literate. One of these types of written work is dictation.

In the process of dictation writing, knowledge about phonetics, lexicology, word-building, morphology and syntax through the dictation of the teacher, students come to memory, apply it in writing. The dictant written will help the teacher in determining the mistakes that the students have made and the reasons for its occurrence. In order to take advantage of these opportunities of the school dictator, and in general for qualifying work, we chose a text consisting of 160 words. The results obtained were calculated by a 20-point criterion (sensitivity, spelling errors and punctuation errors), processed in a correlation way and digital data were obtained.

RESULTS

All the obtained digital data we processed in two stages. At the first stage, using the data of " methods of selection of class intelligences", we separated class intelligences and class stars among the children of 9 academic groups. Their amount amounted to 264 people among 67 children. We would have taken those children as a research group. But in order to ensure full knowledge, we have embarked on second-stage processing, assuming that literacy tests and dictation results provide more accurate data.

For this purpose, when the correlation analysis of digital data obtained from each of the 264 children according to the remaining three methods, a high degree of proportionality was observed among the indicators. This means that the indicators of proportionality indicate that the results of the methodology are directly complementary and psychological qualities in one direction. Therefore, it became possible to summarize the indicators of methodologies and bring them to the indicator of general literacy. The next task is to sort out the most intelligent, advanced students from the complex indicators of these methods. For this purpose, the results of all children were sorted separately on the basis of each methodology, namely "100 words", "50 sentences" and individual indicators from the dictator, and they were given a color (place). From this it became clear that each student was ranked second among 264 examiners depending on the level of performance of a particular methodology. This is due to the fact that the figures have the same content (order numbers according to each methodology), the average order number was obtained from three color indicators for each child.

Thus, based on the generalized and average color of the results, we separated the 30 children who had the lowest score, that is, achieved the highest literacy and dictation scores among the 264 pupils, that is, they were at the top of the list, and called them the experimental group for further research (table).

Table of statistical analysis and indicators of selection methods

Groups	Number of students	100 word method	50 sentence method	Dictation
Experimental group	30 people	$86,9 \pm 3,8$	$68,3 \pm 6,4$	$18,4 \pm 1,5$
The rest of the students	234 people	$68,4 \pm 24,5$	$48,4 \pm 20,9$	$10,8 \pm 6,8$
t		7,4	5,0	5,8
p <		0,001	0,001	0,001

DISCUSSION

In this place, the most important thing is the high level of literacy, and almost all of the students who performed the dictator at an excellent level, either in their class became a class star, or a class nobleman, and among the 67 children who were previously separated. That is, the fact that the data "method of selection of class intelligentsia" has a wide range of bright capabilities

of the class, able to distinguish active students has also been proved in this study. At the same time, as expected, it was observed that these 30 students were different from the remaining 234 students with the level of their literacy indicators and the ability to write dictation without errors ($t=7,4$ $p < 0.001$ on the method "100 Words"; $t=5,0$ $p < 0.001$ on the method "50 sentences"; $t=5,8$ $p < 0.001$ on the

From this information it is possible to conclude that 30 students who have been separated differ in the level of statistical confidence higher than the remaining 234 students with their word-thinking opportunities and mental activity.

Thus, in order to facilitate the educational experiences of the next developer, after the summer holidays, 30 pupils, selected from 9 academic groups of the 7th grade, were combined with the consent of the school administration and formalized as one academic group. Now these are planned to be trained together with the control group on the basis of a special program that has been enriched and accelerated for two years.

If the selection is made correctly and the experimental group is formed correctly, the content of education and the educational process are also carried out in such a way that the mental capacities and directions of the children are appropriately enriched. Therefore, it is necessary that the content and techniques of the proposed education correspond to the requirements of the state educational standards, at the same time be expanded, enriched and at the same time increase the level of intelligence of students, develop their abilities.

In this educational system, programs and plans are made in such a way that it also provides for the formation of the scientific environment in the school by means of a reference to students, writing a statement, discussion of works of art.

CONCLUSIONS

From what has been said, the readability and mastering (as they are traditionally understood) does not always coincide. Nevertheless, some common signs of iqtid students are a high level of thinking and the fact that their achievements in reading from peers are much more advanced by years. Accordingly, such children are required to have a high level of complexity and intensity of reading, the depth of the study of the material, to move from principles to theories and generalizations, and to find an alternative that differs from what is known to all.

Each of the methods chosen to conduct the study helped to analyze the changes in the cognitive processes of the students with the characteristics of high personality and mental development and to determine the characteristics of their development. It was observed that the methods of experimentation in the examiners were aimed at determining their literacy level and mental development. The results obtained through these methods were analyzed and their suitability for diagnosis was determined, reliability was proved using special programs. It is worth noting that all methodologies are scientifically and methodologically justified in solving the problems posed by the scientific hypothesis of the study, the established tasks. The study sought to take a broad approach to the problem of the impact of accelerated learning process on senior students and to make use of the techniques designed to diagnose cognitive processes as widely as possible.

In school conditions, the category of senior students needs conditions in accordance with their capacity and needs for knowledge of Education. Because without it their options will continue to come true. These conditions can also be established in mixed classes with the help of internal differentiation and individualization of Education. However, practice has shown that most of the teachers e'tibori are mainly focused on the problem of students who remain in development. IQT cheats for the development of talented students provide favorable conditions

for programs that are specifically oriented to the general characteristics of such readers and are taken into account in their individual characteristics.

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